

gave straight lines and segmented lines, indicating the formation of single complex in Ce(III)-benzoate and Ce(III)-protocatechuic systems and plural complex formation in Ce(III)-salicylate system (Fig. 1). The stoichiometry of complexes was found to be [Ce(III)-benzoate]^{1:2}, [Ce(III)-(protocatechuic)₂]^{1:2}, [Ce(III)-(salicylate)]^{1:1} and [Ce(III)-(salicylate)₂]^{1:2}. The values of stability constants were calculated by Lingane method⁶ in case of single

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log C_x$ vs $\Delta E_{1/2}$ for 1m M Ce(III) in 1.0 M KCl + 0.01% gelatin at pH. 3.00 ± 0.02 , for
(A) Ce(III)-benzoate \odot
(B) Ce(III)-protocatechuic \triangle
(C) Ce(III)-salicylate \square

species complex, while Deford-Hume⁷ method was used to calculate the formation constants of step wise complex formation of Ce(III)-salicylate system as tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Ce(III) COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Ratio M : L	Stability constant	
			Lingane method	Deford-Hume method
1.	[Ce(III)-benzoate] ^{1:2}	1 : 1	$\log \beta = 4.1$	—
2.	[Ce(III)-(protocatechuic) ₂] ^{1:2}	1 : 2	$\log \beta_2 = 6.28$	—
3.	[Ce(III)-salicylate] ^{1:1}	1 : 1	$\log \beta_1 = 3.6$	3.47
4.	[Ce(III)-(salicylate) ₂] ^{1:2}	1 : 2	$\log \beta_2 = 7.2$	6.98

The stability constants are in agreement with the previously published results of Pr(III) and Nd(III) complexes with benzoic acid, protocatechuic acid and salicylic acid respectively^{1,2}.

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Polarographic Behaviour of Ni(II), Co(II), UO₂(II) and Ge(IV) in Aqueous Mixtures of Propylene Carbonate

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A survey of literature reveals that propylene carbonate, which has a fairly high dielectric constant¹ ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 64.92$), is a new solvent in so far as the polarography of inorganic depolarizers in organic solvents is concerned. With this aim in view the polarographic behaviour of Ni(II), Co(II), UO₂(II) and Ge(IV) has been studied in presence of aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate using 0.1 M NaClO₄ as the supporting electrolyte.

Experimental

Stock solutions of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, UO₂(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (A. R., B.D.H.) and GeO₂ (Fluka, A. R.) were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the final solution to be polarographed was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} M. NaClO₄ (0.1 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte in all the cases. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL 02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M NaClO₄ in open circuit): $h_{corr} = 72.2$ cm, $t = 3.1$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.84$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}. All measurements were made at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Requisite amount of Triton X-100 [$2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$ in the case of Ni(II) and Co(II) and $1.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$ in the case of UO₂(II) and Ge(IV)] was added to suppress the maxima. Purified nitrogen was used for removing dissolved oxygen. The number of electrons (n) involved in the electrode reduction of each of the depolarizers was determined by millicoulometric² method. n is 2 for Ni(II), 2 for Co(II), 1 for each of the two steps of UO₂(II) and 4 for Ge(IV). Knowing the value of n, the diffusion coefficient (D) of the depolarizers was calculated by Ilkovic equation at different percentages of

propylene carbonate. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$) were calculated by Koutecky's method³⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion

Ni(II), Co(II) and Ge(IV) give well-defined waves in the presence of aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate. In the case of $UO_2(II)$, two waves of equal height are obtained in the absence of propylene carbonate but with the addition of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate the second wave gets obliterated. Since each wave of $UO_2(II)$ corresponds to a 1 electron reduction process, the reduction of $UO_2(II)$ in the presence of propylene carbonate takes place as : $UO_2^{2+} + e \rightarrow UO_2^+$.

The waves of all the depolarizers are diffusion-controlled as revealed by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{O_2}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Various criteria of irreversibility⁷⁻¹⁰ indicate that the electrode reactions of Ni(II), Co(II), $UO_2(II)$ and Ge(IV) are irreversible in the presence of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

The values of polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$) for the electrode reactions of Ni(II), Co(II), $UO_2(II)$ and Ge(IV) have been calculated as a function of propylene carbonate.

Influence of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate on the kinetics of electrode reactions of Ni(II), Co(II), $UO_2(II)$ and Ge(IV) :

(i) *Electrode reactions of Ni(II) and Co(II) :* It has been found that both αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$ decrease with increasing amounts (0-20%) of propylene carbonate. It follows from this that the electrode reactions of Ni(II) and Co(II) are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

(ii) *Electrode reaction of $UO_2(II)$:* Each reduction step of $UO_2(II)$ in 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ (in the absence of propylene carbonate) corresponds to 1 electron reduction wave : $UO_2^{2+} + e \rightarrow UO_2^+$ and $UO_2^+ + e \rightarrow UO_2$. The single reduction step occurring in the presence of aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate corresponds to the reduction of UO_2^{2+} to UO_2^+ as this step appears at more positive potentials.

With the addition of 4% (v/v) propylene carbonate both αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$ tend to increase thereby suggesting that the electrode reaction : $UO_2^{2+} + e \rightarrow UO_2^+$ becomes less irreversible. However, further increase (6-20%) of the percentage of propylene carbonate in aqueous mixture renders the above electrode reaction more irreversible as evidenced by the decreasing value of αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$.

(iii) *Electrode reaction of Ge(IV) :* It has been found that with the addition of increasing amounts (0-20%) of propylene carbonate, the kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$ tend to decrease. This implies

that the electrode reaction of Ge(IV) is rendered more irreversible with the addition of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

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Synthesis of Some Substituted Phenylalkylamines

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SUBSTITUTED phenylalkylamines have been synthesised as antiamebic agents and the retention of the dimethoxy moiety was generally regarded as essential for the maintenance of the activity¹⁻⁷.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of some α -(2-ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylphenyl) ethylamines (Scheme 1) and β -(2-ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylphenyl) ethylamines (Scheme 2).

R : a, Et : b ; n-Pr : c ; n-Bu

Scheme 1